

دور اللغة الإنجليزية في تعزيز الهوية العالمية والمحلية من خلال تحليل كتاب (اللغة الإنجليزية لليبيا في القرن الحادي والعشرين)

انتصار الشريف

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المخلص:

أجريت هذه الدراسة لتحليل كتاب اللغة الإنجليزية للقرن الحادي والعشرين لليبي، منهج الصف الخامس الابتدائي، بهدف دراسة كيفية ربط وظائف اللغة الإنجليزية (المفردات والقواعد) بمواضيع محددة من منهج التربية العالمية الشاملة (الهوية، البيئة، والحقوق)، وكيفية توظيف اللغة الإنجليزية في تعزيز الهوية العالمية والمحلية لدى المتعلمين الليبيين. كما هدفت الدراسة إلى تحديد أوجه القصور الملحوظة في الكتاب والتي قد تعيق تعلم اللغة الإنجليزية باعتبارها لغة أجنبية ولتحقيق أهداف البحث وللإجابة عن أسئلته تم اختيار منهجية المراجعة النوعية المنهجية وتحليل المحتوى. وعلى الرغم من وجود بعض أوجه القصور في الكتاب، مثل الاعتماد الكبير على مصادر خارجية وبعض الأخطاء اللغوية التي قد تعيق عملية تعلم الطلاب، إلا أنه يُعدّ منهجًا متطورًا يدمج بنجاح مواضيع التربية العالمية الشاملة في إطاره اللغوي، ويسهم بفعالية في بناء هوية عالمية محلية لدى الطلاب، كما كشف التحليل أن موضوع البيئة هو الموضوع المهيمن.

الكلمات المفتاحية: تدريس اللغة الإنجليزية، تعليم المواطنة العالمية، كتاب اللغة الإنجليزية، كتاب اللغة الإنجليزية للقرن الحادي والعشرين لليبي للصف الخامس الابتدائي.

Fostering Libyan Fifth Grade Pupils' "Glocal" Identity through English Language: An Analysis of the 21st Century English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book

ABSTRACT:

This study was conducted to analyze the *21st Century English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book* to investigate how the English language functions (vocabulary and grammar) are mapped onto specific GCED themes (Identity, Environment and Rights) in the it and how it utilizes the English language to foster a "Glocal" identity for the Libyan learners. It also aimed to identify the noticeable constraints in the book that might hinder EFL learners' learning. Systematic qualitative review and content analysis design were chosen to achieve the research objectives and answer the research questions. Although the book had some constraints, such as heavy dependency on external sources and the minor linguistic error that may hindered pupil's learning process, it is a sophisticated curriculum in which GCED themes are successfully integrated into the linguistic framework and the tasks effectively construct pupils' "Glocal" identity. The analysis also revealed that the environment theme is the dominant theme.

Keywords: English Language Teaching (ELT), Global Citizenship Education (GCED), English Language Textbook, 21st Century English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book.

Introduction

In a globalized world, a transformative lifelong approach to learning is needed to establish curriculum components that foster the learners' international awareness and empower them with the competencies they need

to interact with their peers from around the world. Driven by the need to prepare ethical, engaged, globally active learners, the idea of Global Citizenship Education (GCED) emerged. It is an educational approach that aims to empower learners and raise their local and global awareness and build peaceful, tolerant, inclusive, and diverse societies (UNESCO, 2015). GCED is a transformative lifelong approach to learning that “plays a crucial role in promoting solidarity and empowering people of all ages to make a meaningful impact in their communities, both locally and globally” (UNESCO, n.d.). The position of GCED is seen as a framework that aims to foster peaceful, tolerant, and sustainable societies (UNESCO, 2015). Its core thematic domains are centered on three themes: Identity, Environment, and Rights (UNESCO, 2015). Learners’ self-awareness and belonging is represented in the Identity theme. Learners’ ecological stewardship and sustainability are signified by the Environment theme. Learners’ awareness of human dignity, equity, and justice are raised through the Rights theme (UNESCO, 2015).

English now is considered a global lingua franca, which means that it can serve as a global language bridge. The role of the English language has shifted. It changed from being a foreign language into being a global lingua franca. Accordingly, ELT offers an outstanding framework to integrate GCED (Nuri, 2025). It provides ELT educators and teachers with a unique advantage to embed the core tenets of GCED into language curricula (Nuri, 2025).

Interest in the intersection of GCED and ELT instruction has gained increasing scholarly attention lately that reflects wider recognition of the idea that language education goes beyond the mere linguistic competence acquisition. The integration of GCED changes the purpose of learning the language from learning a foreign language to learning a global language that cultivates learners’ respect of cultural diversity and facilitates global

awareness and communication. The roles of teachers also shift from mere language teachers to becoming facilitators who enhance learners' awareness and understanding of global issues, while also helping them become active participants in finding solutions for global issues (Nuri, 2025; Pramata & Yuliati, 2016).

Researchers noted that the sole task of ELT instructors is not only to teach vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation, and receptive and productive language skills; they are also they responsible for developing their learners' awareness and understanding as well as training them to become active participants in finding solutions for global issues (Nuri, 2025; Pramata & Yuliati, 2016). Accordingly, ELT textbooks are required to embed these themes within language activities.

Textbooks are the foundational mediums for curriculum delivery that shape the linguistic skills and instill cultural values, identities, and global perspectives (Gray, 2023; Tomlinson, 2012). Accordingly, the analysis of textbooks through the GCED framework is of significance to understand how language pedagogy intersects with the local and global subjectivities' formation. This review explores three interrelated dimensions that include the mapping of English language functions onto GCED themes, fostering a "glocal" identity through EFL textbooks, and the constraints in the textbooks that hinder learners' educational development.

ELT textbooks were utilized to deliver GCED objectives in meaningful tasks. Review of current research findings showed that these studies heavily favored surface-level thematic analysis through tracking the frequency of certain topics. For instance, Sahli and Belaid (2022) scanned the Algerian secondary foreign language education textbook to examine how the ideals of GCED and competency are covered, respectively. They depended on the

PISA framework for their evaluation of global competency and concluded that textbooks adequately cover the themes of GCED. Ait-Biuzid (2020) designed a checklist based on UNESCO's framework and combined both qualitative and quantitative techniques to evaluate three second-year high school level textbooks: Gateway to English 2, Insights into English 2, and Ticket to English 2. He concluded that even though the three textbooks included activities that promoted aspects of citizenship, their constraints were in developing learners' critical perspectives towards global citizenship.

Finally, even though there is a growing body of research that explores English language functions in EFL textbooks, with particular focus on vocabulary and grammar, studies that explore mapping English language functions onto GCED themes in EFL textbooks seem to be underexplored. In addition, studies that explored the integration of GCED and fostering a "Glocal" identity through Libyan EFL textbooks are scarce. To address this gap, this study aimed to analyze the *21st Century English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book* to evaluate the alignment between the GCED objectives and the linguistic functions.

Thus, this study aimed to achieve the following research objectives:

1. Investigate how the English language functions (vocabulary and grammar) are mapped onto specific GCED themes (Identity, Environment and Rights) in the *21st Century English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book*.
2. Explore how the *21st Century English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book* utilize the English language to foster a "Glocal" identity for the Libyan learners.

3. Identify the noticeable constraints in the *21st Century English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book* that might hinder EFL learners' learning.

To achieve the study's objectives, three research questions were raised:

1. How are English language functions (vocabulary and grammar) mapped onto specific GCED themes (Identity, Environment and Rights) in *the 21st Century English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book*?
2. How does the *21st Century English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book* utilize the English language to foster a "Glocal" identity for the Libyan learners?
3. What are the noticeable constraints in the *21st Century English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book* that might hinder EFL learners' learning?

This study serves as a bridge that offers empirical evidence signifying how grammatical and lexical structures facilitate or constrain English language learners' global competencies' development. The significance of this study lies in that it opens doors for further critical exploration into the connection between language pedagogy and civic education. It shifts focus from surface-level thematic analysis to microlinguistic and in-depth analysis. The findings of the study are of significance for ELT educators and practitioners, curriculum developers, textbook writers/designers, and applied linguistics and educational researchers, especially in the Libyan context.

Methodology

As the study aimed to explore how 21st Century English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book fosters Libyan fifth graders' "glocal" identity through English Language and to identify the noticeable weaknesses in the English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book that might hinder EFL pupils' learning, a qualitative research design was chosen. A systematic qualitative review and content analysis design were chosen to identify how the linguistic elements align with Global Citizenship Education (GCED) objectives.

The primary data source is the Libyan public schools' grade 5 pupil's book entitled "21st Century English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book" that is published by Garnet Publishing in 2019 (first edition) for the Libyan Ministry of Education. Vibrant colors and a clean layout are featured in the front and back covers and the interior of the textbook. The textbook is explicitly branded as "21st CENTURY" curriculum. It incorporates a picture dictionary, cut-out word cards, and a word list. The textbook consists of real-life photographs and cartoon illustrations. Interactive game boards, such as Snakes and Ladders, are utilized to stimulate the Libyan pupils' interest.

The book consists of eight units, two of which are mainly dedicated to revisions: Unit 4 (4 lessons) and Unit 8 (4 lessons). Each unit is divided into 8 lessons. The book also includes a Word List for all of the units. The book content covers topics that are related to the pupils' real-life circumstances, such as school life, playground safety, and local and international geography.

- Unit 1, "Our School," 8 Lessons: New Friends, Our Playground, Playground Rules, What's in My School Bag, What's the Difference, Packing My School Bag, At the School Shop, and The Lion and the Mouse.
- Unit 2, "Around the World," 8 Lessons: Where are you from?, I'm from Libya., Are they the same?, Different Days, About Time, Geography: Country Profile, Guess what it is!, and City Mouse and Village Mouse.
- Unit 3, "Open Day," 8 Lessons: Welcome to our Open Day!, What do you want to drink?, What do you want to eat?, At the Races, What's wrong?, What's first?, Making a Poster, and Races on the Sports Field.
- Unit 4, "Revision (1)," 4 Lessons: The Challenge, My Progress, The Magic Bird, and Snakes and Ladders.
- Unit 5, "Places to See," 8 Lessons: Different Places, A School Trip, On the Train, At the Waterfall, Mountains in Libya, Higher and Highest, Let's play a game!, and A Trip to the Museum.
- Unit 6, "Places to See," 8 Lessons: Wh- Questions, Yesterday, Question Game, Nadia's Grandma, At the Cinema, Where did you go?, There was../There were, and The Little Brown Bird.

- Unit 7, “In the Past,” 8 Lessons: The School Challenge, You need a ruler, What do they need?, must / mustn't, Challenge Rules, Maths and Art, English and Sport, and The Big Bike Race.
- Unit 8, “Revision (2),” 4 Lessons: Test your partner, My Progress, Ice-creams for everyone!, and A Pronunciation Game.

These topics are discussed with basic grammar such as adjectives and time telling. To build their vocabulary, the topics are introduced to the pupils with multifaceted pedagogical tools that include songs and dialogues. Each of the units ends with an illustrated story such as The Lion and the Mouse in Unit 1, City Mouse and Village Mouse in Unit 2, Races on the Sports Field in Unit 3, A Trip to the Museum in Unit 5, The Little Brown Bird in Unit 6, and The Big Bike Race in Unit 7. Finally, the book includes a detailed book map that outlines the linguistic objectives for each unit.

The analysis is grounded in the Global Citizenship Education (GCED) framework and the concept of globalization. The GCED framework was used to categorize the book content into three themes: Identity, Environment, and Rights and Responsibilities. Globalization is the lens by which the textbook was used to understand how the textbook synthesized Libyan culture and heritage with global English language functions. It was the lens by which the textbook was analyzed to verify how it fostered pupils' “glocal” identity through an international language.

The textbook analysis procedures were in five phases. In the first phase, the Book Map and the Word List were read carefully to identify the intended language functions and vocabulary of each unit. In the second phase, thematic coding of linguistic functions was conducted. Each unit's vocabulary and grammar were mapped onto the GCED themes: Identity, Environment, and Rights. In the third phase, comparative “glocal” evaluation was conducted by identifying the Libyan landmarks as the local markers and international peers as global markers, which determined how the “glocal” identity was constructed. In the fourth phase, the textbook units were reviewed to identify linguistic errors and source dependency. In the final phase, an analysis of the cross-curricular and cognitive load was conducted to identify the activities in which the pupils were required to use non-linguistics skills while listening or reading in English.

This analysis process was first conducted manually through different phases of careful line-by-line reading and coding and then was done by utilizing Formula Bot (2026) to ensure that the findings are not affected by the researcher's biases. Formula Bot is an AI-powered data analytics platform. A PDF of the textbook was uploaded to Formula Bot a series of interactions through questioning and critical comments and thematic analysis was conducted. Finally, the Formula Bot findings were compared with the researcher's findings to create the themes and answer the research questions.

Results

The main aim of this study was to investigate English language function alignment with three specific themes of GCED: Identity, Environment, and Rights in the *21st Century English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book*. Three research questions were raised to investigate how English language functions in the *21st Century English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book* (vocabulary and grammar) were mapped onto specific GCED themes, how the textbook utilized the English language to foster a "glocal" identity for the Libyan fifth grade pupils, and identify the noticeable constraints in the textbook that might hinder EFL pupils' learning. Based on the analysis of the eight units of the textbook, Table 2 shows the distribution of GCED themes in the 56 lessons of the book. As can be seen, Identity theme is the dominant theme with nearly sixty percent of all GCED lessons. Following that is the Environment theme, accounting for twenty-four percent of all GCED lessons. The Rights themes is the least represented theme, with only 16% of all GCED lessons.

The qualitative analysis findings demonstrate the systematic integration of linguistic development with global citizenship education in the curriculum. The findings also revealed some constraints that might have affected the learners' learning. The following sections present the findings of the analysis of the specified Libyan textbook are presented in according with the three research questions.

Table 1. GECD Themes' Distribution in the Textbook

GCED Theme	Number of Lessons	Approximate Percentage %	Examples from the Book
Identity	33.5	59,8%	Self-introductions, family members, country names, capital cities, and languages.
Environment	13.5	24.1%	Mountains, desert, oil fields, oases, waterfall, and weather conditions.
Rights	9	16.1%	School rules, playground safety, modals of obligation (must/mustn't), and cooperation.

Mapping Language Functions onto GCED Themes

The first research question aimed to investigate how the English language functions (vocabulary and grammar) are mapped onto specific GCED themes (Identity, Environment and Rights) in the *21st Century English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book*. The findings showed that the textbook established a deliberate alignment between English language functions (vocabulary and grammar) and the GCED themes of Identity, Environment, and Rights.

Identity

The Identity theme is the most widespread theme nearly across every unit of the *21st Century English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book*. The mapping of language functions follows a developmental trajectory. The lessons evolve from a focus on self-description and personal identity to constructing identity through descriptions of belonging, preferences, and heritage. Revision units are designed to reinforce the identity theme through recycling of what has been learned (Units 4, 8).

Self-Description and Personal Identity (Units 1, 2, 6)

Learners' identity is constructed through language for self-description and ownership, personal description to cultural and national identity, and through the lens of family and past self-description. The linguistic foundation for GCED identity enables

learners' self-representation and interpersonal comparison, moving from self-focused identity to being situated within a national and linguistic community and intergenerational connections through the construction of personal identity that is rooted in family heritage.

- **Vocabulary:** Vocabulary included personal attributes such as name, age, and grade; physical descriptions; school-related belongings; and shifts to countries, cities, languages, and nationalities. This is exemplified by words such as “Nadia,” “9,” “Grade 3” (page 8), “short black hair” (page 8), “ruler,” “pencil,” “sharpener,” “crayons” (page 14), “Libya,” “England,” “Tripoli,” “London,” “English,” “Arabic,” “Libyan,” and “British” (page 29).
- **Grammar:** Grammatical resources include simple present, possessives, and self-identification. Language functions for self-expression focus on teaching the pupils how to introduce themselves and establish origins. The pupils learn to use the simple present to state personal facts, such as using the verb to be to say their names or their ages. For example, “Hello, I’m Yousif, and I’m 9” (page 8). Inquiry functions and identifying native language are used to foster pupils’ national and global identities. Inquiry functions, such as “Where are you from?” (page 26), and native language identifying, such as “I speak Arabic” (page 29), are introduced to the pupils to foster pupils’ national and global identities. To teach pupils how to differentiate personal identity, comparative adjectives are used. For example, they learn to use “taller than” and “younger than,” such as “I am taller than Lina” (page 17).

Belonging, Preferences, and Heritage (Units 3, 5, and 7)

Learners’ identities are constructed through language for personal belongings, needs, abilities, and cooperation and by emphasizing cultural identity and heritage awareness.

- **Vocabulary:** Vocabulary includes the months of the year (page 45); drinks such as cola, orange juice, and lemonade (pages 46–47); food such as “cakes,” “sandwiches,” and “pizza” (page 45); clothes such as “T-shirt” and “trousers” (page 51); and places such as “Libyan Museum,” “Ubari Oasis,” and “Nafusa Mountains,” and words such as “statue,” “painting,” and “mosaic” (page 69).
- **Grammar:** Grammatical resources include possessives, asking personal questions using “when” and “whose,” expressing preferences, describing national places and

heritage, and articulating individual needs. For instance, in Lesson 4 of Unit 3, pupils learn how to use possessive nouns by adding an apostrophe and an s ('s), such as Yousif's T-shirt, Lina's egg, and Nadia's trainers (pages 51 & 52).

Environment

The Environment theme is mapped to progress from the immediate school environment to broader geographical and natural landscapes. It is developed to empower the pupils with specific linguistic functions that help them describe, locate, compare, and move. Pupils use the English language for show their appreciation to landscapes, geography, and natural diversity. The units particularly emphasize Libya's natural features as representative of the pupils' own country. They learn to use sophisticated grammatical structures and vocabulary to rank, compare, and evaluate these features. Revision units are designed to reinforce the identity theme through recycling of what has been learned (Units 4, 8).

School and Local Environment (Units 1, 2, 3)

Units 1, 2, and 3 are built on the Environment theme by learning about the school environment and physical space. GCED Environment is connected to the pupils' immediate surroundings by using specific vocabulary and certain grammatical forms. Their use of comparatives for environmental descriptions involves them in analytical thinking about the natural world surrounding them.

- **Vocabulary.** Vocabulary in Unit 1 is focused on playground equipment such as "swings" and "slide;" shop items such as "cookies" and "notebooks;" and preposition words, such as "middle" and "bottom." Vocabulary in Unit 2 expands to a wider world and covers geography, natural features, and resources. In Unit 3, vocabulary is mostly focused on school items, such as "classroom," "sports field," "poster," and "open day." Some weather and nature words appeared in the illustrations.
- **Grammar.** Grammar covers the present continuous for actions and movement, prepositions of movement, location language, comparatives and descriptions, prepositions of place, and "there is/there are." These forms help the pupils link English language practice with place-based knowledge, which raises their environmental awareness.

Natural Landscape and Geography (Units 5, 6, and 7)

Units 5, 6, and 7 are built on the Environment theme as they are built on geography and nature, and their language functions are built onto the physical world's descriptive functions and comparative structures.

- **Vocabulary.** Vocabulary is focused on natural features and landscapes in geography, such as “mountains,” “streams,” “deserts,” “forests,” “rivers,” “lakes,” “waterfalls,” and “fields.” It also includes vocabulary for places and spatial language, such as “school,” “library,” “supermarket,” “zoo,” and “playground.” Movement manner words, such as “quickly,” “slowly,” “carefully,” and “loudly” are included.
- **Grammar.** Grammar functions give the pupils the chance to create geographical profiles. Page 37 includes an example of that: “Libya is a big country. It has high mountains and a dry desert.” Grammar includes comparatives and superlatives, descriptive sentences, prepositions of place, past existence, and location questions. Superlatives are used to create comparisons of environmental scale. For example, the Libyan desert is described as the “largest” in the following sentences: “Libya has the 3rd largest desert in the world” (page 37). Another example is in identifying the “highest” mountain.

Rights

Even though the Rights themes is the least represented theme with only 16% of all GCED lessons, it is considered to be the most distinctive theme of GCED themes. This is because its mapping connects language functions to rules, safety, responsibility, and social participation. Grammatical structures are used to express obligations, prohibitions, and regulations. Revision units are designed to reinforce the identity theme through recycling of what have been learned (Units 4, 8).

Rules, Safety, and Conduct (Units 1, 3, and 5)

Rules, safety, and helping others are introduced in Unit 1 and then expanded in Unit 3 by focusing on participation, fair competition, and polite interactions. In Unit 5, acting respectfully in shared spaces is presented through classroom and public behavior rules.

- **Vocabulary.** Vocabulary is focused on safety and conduct verbs and expressions; ordinal numbers for ranking and participation; transactional language for stalls, food, and prices; and adverbs. Examples of verbs and adverbs from the three units

include “stand,” “push,” “hold on,” “go fast,” “balance,” “help,” “sit,” “eat,” “talk,” “walk,” “forget,” “quietly,” and “loudly.”

- **Grammar.** Grammar features imperatives for giving rules and instructions; negative imperatives; polite requests; comparatives for fairness or comparisons; imperatives for rules and safety; polite and responsible behavior in public spaces; and making decisions in particular situations. For instance, pupils learn that negative imperatives like “Do not...” and “Don’t...” are used to emphasize safe behavior, rules, and responsibility in the community.

Obligation, Education, and Participation (Units 6, and 7)

Obligation, education, and participation are introduced in units six and seven.

- **Vocabulary.** Vocabulary is focused on safety and conduct verbs and expressions; ordinal numbers for ranking and participation; transactional language for stalls, food, and prices, and adverbs. Examples of verbs and adverbs from the three units include “stand,” “push,” “hold on,” “go fast,” “balance,” “help,” “sit,” “eat,” “talk,” “walk,” “forget,” “quietly,” and “loudly.”
- **Grammar.** Grammar features imperatives for giving rules and instructions, negative imperatives, polite requests, comparatives for fairness or comparisons, imperatives, and the modal verbs “must” and “mustn’t.” Pupils learn about rules and citizenship in this theme, which are integrated through modals of obligations and negative imperatives. They learn about school conduct and social responsibility by using functions such as “must” and “mustn’t,” whereas they learn about playground safety by using imperatives. Examples of that include “I must help my family,” “I mustn’t shout in class,” “You mustn’t look at your friend’s answer,” “Don’t stand on the swing,” and “You must help your friends.”

Fostering a “Glocal” Identity

The second research question aimed to investigate how the *21st Century English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil’s Book* utilizes the English language to foster a “glocal” identity for the Libyan fifth grade pupils. The findings showed that the curriculum employs English to foster a “glocal” identity by embedding the learners’ local culture and heritage while providing them with the necessary cross-cultural competencies that are needed for global

communication. The textbook fosters Libyan “glocal” identity by localizing English, framing local heritage and geography in English, connecting local values to global citizenship norms, utilizing global language functions for local needs, and integrating 21st century competencies with local content.

Localizing English (All Units)

The most visible strategy of constructing a glocal identity is the systematic use of Libyan names, settings, and symbols. The textbook designers were dedicated to ensuring that the textbook’s social world that is presented in English mirrors that Libyan fifth grade pupil’s real-life social world. For instance, the characters are given local names, such as Yousif, Nadia, Kareem, and Lina in Lesson 1 of Unit 1 and Adel in Lesson 2 of Unit 2. Another strategy can be noticed in including visual clues that reinforce a sense of national pride that is represented by the Libyan flag. The Libyan flag is integrated into most of the school scenes and maps (pages 9 and 29 as examples). In Lesson 2 of Unit 2, fifth graders learn about their mother tongue by answering the question, “What language do you speak? I speak Arabic” (page 29). Another example is in the use of the Libyan dinar (LYD) as a form of all financial transactions (page 48). This purpose is to reinforce the idea of localization and help the Libyan pupils feel that the English language used in the textbook belongs to their world and their world belongs to it.

Framing Local Heritage and Geography in English (Units 2, 5, and 8)

To frame local heritage and geography in English, the textbook gives the chance to Libyan fifth grade pupils to learn how to describe their country’s cultural and physical characteristics in the globally used and understood English language. Local geography is represented in tasks in which the pupils describe Libyan landmarks in English. They learn how to use English to describe specific Libyan landmarks, such as the Sahara Desert, Nafusa Mountains, and the Ubari Oasis. Page 37, for instance, includes information about the Sahara desert and it is described as follows: “Libya has the 3rd largest desert in the world. The Sahara desert is as big as the United States” (p. 37). Nafusa Mountains are described as follows: “Nafusa Mountains are in the west of Libya. They are 968 metres high” (p. 76). Finally, the Ubari Oasis is described as follows: “The Ubari Oasis lies between the Sahara dessert and the very young sand dunes of the Idehan Ubari desert” (p. 77). Libyan cultural heritage is presented to them through information about the Libyan Museum

(Lesson 1 of Unit 5). They learn words such as “ancient,” “statue,” and “mosaic” to discuss Libyan history (p. 69). This presentation of local features in English positions Libya within a global conversation in the pupils’ minds. This conveys the worth of their country and the idea that it is worth describing in English to their peers around the world.

Connecting Local Values to Global Citizenship Norms (Units 1, and 7)

The textbook’s mechanism for connecting local Libyan values to global citizenship norms is achieved through the integration of Islamic duties and family obligations that are expressed in English and connected to universal citizenship values. For instance, in lesson 4 of Unit 7, pupils learn how to use an expression to talk about one of the Five Pillars of Islam that is praying, known as Salat, by saying, “I must pray” (p. 110). They learn to use the modal “must” as an obligation signal in English to articulate sacred religious duty. Other examples include stories about helping others. Polite requests and social harmony are evidenced in Lesson 3 of Unit 7 and Lesson 8 of Unit 1. In Lesson 3 the pupils practice polite requests using “Can I borrow your?” whereas Lesson 8 fosters kindness by bringing the globally recognized fable of “The Lion and the Mouse” to the Libyan English language classroom. Another example of using stories to foster certain morals or manners is in the bike-race story entitled “The Big Bike Race” presented in Lesson 8 of Unit 7. In this story the pupils learn how children helped each other during competitions, which promotes students’ understanding of cooperation and fairness. Finally, the “Ice-creams for everyone” story of Lesson 3 of Unit 8 introduces the act of helping elders to cross the road to the Libyan pupils in English. It teaches them respect and community safety.

Utilizing Global Language Functions for Local Needs (All units)

To connect Libyan fifth grade pupils to the global community, English language is positioned as a bridge that helps them engage with diverse cultures and global standards. This is achieved through international peer exchange and global literacy standards. In Unit 2, entitled “Around the World,” Libyan fifth grade pupils are introduced to their peers from around the world representing various nations. They learn how to use English as a tool for international friendship. For instance, they meet Sam from England; Liz from America; Pedro and Alex from Brazil; Anna from Russia; and Amy from China (p. 26). Additionally, the book teaches them global literacy standards. They learn that names’ and country names’ first letters must be capitalized to align with global English writing conventions.

Examples are presented in names such as Adel, Sam, Liz, Anna, and Amy and countries such as Libya, England, America, Brazil, Russia, and China (p. 26). They also learn to use globally transferable language functions for communicative purposes that are locally relevant to them. For instance, they learn to say statements such as “I’m from Libya” or “Can I borrow yours?” as forms of globally standard language functions.

The textbook also cultivates a comparative perspective by helping the fifth grade pupils understand their country’s globally distinctive position by comparing Libya with other countries. This is established through cross-cultural comparison, environmental scalability, and economic awareness. Cross-cultural comparison is presented to pupils by training them to use comparative grammar to analyze differences between nations. For example, in Lesson 3 of Unit 2 entitled “Are they the same?,” they learn how to use “smaller than” to compare two countries and “hotter” to compare temperatures. For example, they read “England is smaller than Libya” and have to decide whether to choose “Yes” or “No.” The book also teaches Libyan pupils that their local environment is part of a larger global system by applying universal geographical terms such as “mountain,” “river,” and “desert.” They are introduced to them as part of local and global features in Unit 2 in which they learn about Nafusa Mountains and other local and global features. Libyan fifth grade pupils’ economic awareness is raised by learning about Libya’s role in the local and international economy. For instance, they use English to describe oil fields and the importance of oil in Lesson 6 of Unit 2 of the *21st Century English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil’s Book*.

Integrating 21st Century Competencies with Local Content (Units 1, 3, 5, 7)

The final mechanism is the integration of 21st century competencies with local content. Competencies like communication, collaboration, critical thinking, project-based learning, email writing, and form completion are integrated with local content. Throughout the textbook, 21st century skills are integrated and provide evidence that the book not only aims to enhance the pupils’ linguistic competence but also aims for enhancing their broader cognitive and social competencies that are required in the contemporary globalized world. They are embedded as Libyan scenarios in the Open Day in Unit 3, the mini-project on a Libyan desert oasis in Unit 5, and the email-style challenge in Unit 7. 21st century communication is represented to Libyan fifth graders through reading and writing emails. This is particularly presented in Lesson 5 of Unit 3 entitled Open Day. In this lesson,

students listen to an audio of the script and read Suzan's email to Lina, in which she wrote about their school open day (p. 53).

Pedagogical and Linguistic Constraints

The final research question aimed to identify the noticeable constraints in the 21st century English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book that might hinder Libyan EFL learners' learning. The findings revealed that despite its modern design, five constraints were identified that might have affected the Libyan learning process or hindered learning, which included excessive linguistic and cognitive load, limited productive language opportunities, heavy dependency on resources and components, insufficient scaffolding, and linguistic and typographical errors.

Excessive Linguistic and Cognitive Load

The most prominent constraint is the excessive linguistic and cognitive load, as many of the textbook units introduce Libyan fifth grade pupils to a substantial amount of new vocabulary and grammar that may become overwhelming to them. For example. In Unit 1, the pupils are introduced to self-introduction language, possessives, comparatives, and other grammatical structures without giving them enough chance to fully master these structures. In Unit 2, for example, pupils are asked to use comparatives with no clear rule explanations. In addition, there are complex cross-curricular non-linguistic tasks that the pupils may find overwhelming. For instance, the dual demand on mathematical precision and language processing may hinder pupils' chances of vocabulary and grammar acquisition. One of the examples is on page 114; there is a Math challenge in which they listen to an audio and then draw a 4 cm x 2 cm rectangular, a 3 cm x 3 cm square, and a triangle in their own size. They may find it difficult to listen, follow instructions, and draw the required shapes in the exact metric measurements.

Limited Productive Language Opportunities

Analysis revealed limited productive opportunities as one of the major constraints. This limitation is because the majority of the tasks are focused excessively on the receptive skills: listening and reading. As productive skills, speaking and writing tasks are considered to be limited compared to the number of tasks devoted to the receptive skills. This trend is evidenced in Units 1, 3, 5, 6, and 7. These units are controlled with filling gaps, ticking

boxes, matching, or repeating dialogue sets, which limit the pupils' chances of speaking or writing.

Heavy Dependency on Resources and Components

Successful implementation of the curriculum depends heavily on a multi-component system that includes audio tracks and an activity book. Most of the lessons include listening activities and supporting activities in the activity book. For instance, in Units 1, 3, 5, 6, and 7, most of the activities heavily rely on "Listen" tracks. The lack of the availability of both of them affects successful implementation and therefore hinders pupils' learning. For instance, there are 17 tasks that ask the pupils to do something (read, sing, say, practice, etc.). As many of the textbook activities require physical resources' availability, the unavailability of the resources will become learning barriers. For instance, the textbook included many creative activities that require supplies, such as different kinds of papers, crayons, scissors, and glue. The successful implementation of tasks labeled as "P for Project" and "Challenge" requires resource-rich environments. Accordingly, these tasks will not be successful in resource-constrained classrooms.

Insufficient Scaffolding

The temporary support that is given to learners so that they can complete the required tasks or acquire the targeted skills is known as scaffolding. Scaffolding is of significance for all English language learners; more specifically, it is needed for struggling learners. Analysis revealed scaffolding as one of the constraints, as it is consistently insufficient throughout the pupils' book, which leaves the learners without the needed support that would help them bridge the gap between their current knowledge and abilities and what is required in the tasks. Evidence of insufficient scaffolding can be found in units 1, 2, 3, 5, and 6. Unit 1 includes tasks that give pupils a limited number of models that lead them to find the tasks difficult because of the inadequate scaffolding. Unit 2 includes grammatical tasks with limited rules explanations. Limited scaffolding for speaking and writing is clear in Units 3 and 6, as learners are moved quickly from recognizing full sentences to producing them, which may lead students with lower language levels to struggle.

Linguistic and Typographical Errors

The book contains notable spelling and typographical errors that may interfere with the pupils' learning and lead them to learn incorrect forms of English. For example, "desert" is misspelled with double "s" in the following sentence: "The Ubari Oasis lies between the Sahara dessert and the very young sand dunes of the Idehan Ubari desert" (English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book, 2019, p. 77). On page 137, there is a prepositional error in the Word List section, as "fallen off" is written as "fallen of" in the example sentence. On pages 103 and 114, the word "Maths" is introduced. Even though the spelling is not considered wrong in British English, the American version of the word is more popular, which might lead to confusion. It should have been elaborated to learners that there are two spellings: the British spelling has an 's' as it is considered an abbreviation for 'mathematics' that ends with the 's', whereas the American English spelling does not include the letter 's'.

Discussion

The analysis of *21st Century English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book* revealed that the book established a deliberate alignment between English language functions and GCED themes. It concurrently establishes a sophisticated design even with the notable five constraints. The discussion aims to synthesize the main findings: the mapping of English language functions onto GCED themes, the construction of "glocal" identity, and the identification of the textbook constraints.

Deep Integration of GCED

The findings of the first research question revealed that the *21st Century English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book* successfully achieved deep integration of GCED themes onto English. The Libyan fifth grade English language textbook's intentional employment of vocabulary and grammar as practical tools that serve as drivers that help the pupils to achieve GCED-themed communication goals. The grammar-themed correspondences for the themes of Environment and Rights are not random additions to the textbook. On the contrary, they reflect a design that was chosen deliberately to introduce the pupils to grammatical structures they needed to produce for effective communication that is associated with GCED themes. Functional alignment appears to be the main reason for the meaningful content-language integration of GCED themes in the *21st Century English*

for *Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book*. The UNESCO (2021) framework for global learning emphasizes the GCED dimensions in foreign language teaching. The analyzed Libyan textbook implemented this framework by using language functions as the primary tool for expressing personal and cultural identity, comparing environmental features, and articulating rules and responsibilities.

Glocal Identity Construction through Localization

The approach the textbook maintained to construct the Libyan pupils' glocal identity can be considered one of the strengths of the textbook. This is because the textbook fostered Libyan "glocal" identity through five interconnected mechanisms that included localizing English, framing local heritage and geography in English, connecting local values to global citizenship norms, utilizing global language functions for local needs, and integrating 21st century competencies with local content. The findings contribute to the existing debate about the relationship between English language and local identity in World Englishes and ELT. Canagaraja's (2020) contemporary paradigm shift in critical sociolinguistics and applied linguistics redefines how global English is viewed by shifting focus on the active agency of local speakers. He called for revising the language politics agenda and recognizing the agency of local communities. The analyzed textbook provides a concrete exemplification of English that is presented as a communicative resource that the Libyan pupils use to perform a profound local act in a global language.

Deep Integration Undermined by Some Constraints

Despite its successful integration of GCED themes and glocal identity construction through localization, analysis of the *21st Century English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book* identified some constraints. that might have affected the Libyan learning process or hindered learning. The five constraints included excessive linguistic and cognitive load, limited productive language opportunities, heavy dependency on resources and components, insufficient scaffolding, and linguistic and typographical errors. Thus, a central paradox is created, which means that the textbook designers need to understand the causes of these underlying contradictions and find solutions for the identified insufficiencies.

Conclusion

In light of the findings, the study concludes that even though the *21st Century English for Libya Primary 5 Pupil's Book* had some constraints that may hinder the pupils'

learning process, the book is a sophisticated GCED theme-based curriculum. GCED themes are successfully integrated into the book's linguistic framework. The tasks in the book effectively construct Libyan fifth graders' "glocal" identity and empower them to become informed global citizens. However, heavy dependency on external sources and the minor linguistic error are some of the constraints that the textbook developers will take into their account in future editions as well as Libyan teachers who are using this textbook to teach their pupils.

Given the findings, a number of pedagogical implications need to be addressed. This shift into a GCED theme-based curriculum calls for Libyan EFL teachers' attention. They need to understand that this shift is not only in the textbook, but it also changes their roles from mere language instructors to becoming facilitators of social and global awareness. Additionally, the analysis highlighted the integration of multiple academic disciplines such as Math, Art, and Social Studies, which suggests that the English language is becoming interdisciplinary. This calls for EFL teachers' attention, as well, so that they understand they are required to be involved in multiple areas while teaching the pupils the language functions.

It is recommended that the Libyan Ministry of Education provide Libyan EFL teachers with training opportunities to enhance their understanding of the GCED theme-based curriculum in ELT and enhance their teaching skills. The ministry is also required to ensure full accessibility to all the course components. Teachers are required to integrate the audio tracks, synchronize the book activities with the activity book, and utilize the teacher resources such as posters, pictures, cards, and word cards. It is also recommended that the ministry provide the required resources to help the teachers implement project-based teaching successfully. Additionally, managing cognitive load is recommended, especially for cross-curricular tasks. Finally, teachers should prevent the fossilizing of mistakes by correcting the typographical errors and notifying their pupils about them simultaneously. Addressing the textbook weaknesses and limitations, better editions of the current editions may be printed.

The components of the 21st Century English for Libya Primary 5 include the "Pupil's Book," the "Activity Book," the "Teacher's Book," the "Audio," and the "Teacher Resources." In this study, analysis was limited to the pupils' book. This study is also limited in that its

findings are based on content analysis of the pupils' book only and not based on any empirical classroom observations or pupils' and teachers' perceptions and views.

Thus, further research studies are needed in terms of pupils' interaction with the textbook and the audio material. An analysis of all of the components of the 21st century English for Libya Primary 5 is also needed to understand how the three themes are integrated into the language functions. A comparative analysis is also recommended. Finally, a study that investigates whether the textbook enhances the pupil's critical thinking is needed.

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